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DEALING WITH A RESURGENT CHINA

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Research Notes

Mapping the Social Discourse in Chinese Art and Literature of the Xi Jinping Era

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Introductory remarks

This document provides the extended version of the discussion presented in the Policy Brief *Not all happy: Voices of social critique in contemporary Chinese culture* by Marcin Jacoby, Anna Gryzkiewicz, Piotr Machajek, and František Reismüller (SWPS University). This in-depth supplement names specific authors, works, dates of releasing/publishing/staging, and traces the specific subtopics within the bigger clusters proposed in the brief.

CONTENTS

SOCIAL AND INTERPERSONAL DYNAMICS - 3 -

ECONOMIC AND STRUCTURAL PRESSURES - 4 -

PERSONAL IDENTITY AND WELL-BEING - 7 -

WAYS OF VOICING SOCIAL CRITIQUE..... - 9 -

REFERENCES..... - 12 -

Social and Interpersonal Dynamics

Across various media—be it film, theatre, literature, or visual arts—Chinese artists are uncovering and challenging the intricate layers of family relationships, generational divides, and disillusionment felt by both young and old. One of these perspectives is **parent-child relations**, specifically the generational divides and the examination of family bonds. Numerous works, particularly films, focus on themes of generational clash (*Girls Always Happy*, *Rouqing Shi* 柔情史, 2018, dir. Yang Mingmin 杨明明; *Spring Tide*, *Chun Chao* 春潮, 2019, dir. Yang Lina 杨荔钠), or alienation within the family (*Send Me to the Clouds*, *Song Wo Shang Qing Yun* 送我上青云, 2019, dir. Teng Congcong 滕丛丛). The topic of parental care and family duty is also explored in works by young visual artists (*My Father and Me*, *Fu Lia* 父俩, 2022, Li Xin 李鑫). **Family strains, broken families and “left-behind” children** appear in Gan Xiao'er's 甘小二 *Country Far Away* (*Sun Mao* 榉卯, 2017), Wei Shujun's 魏书钧 *Striding into the Wind* (*Ye Ma Fen Zong* 野马分鬃, 2020), and Bai Xue's 白雪 *The Crossing* (*Guo Chun Tian* 过春天, 2018). The topic of high expectations of mothers towards their daughters — a pressure passed down from generation to generation, and overprotectiveness are explored further in Lu Zhan's 陆展 theatre production *On Her Own* (*Bang yu Zhenzhu* 蚌与珍珠). Another significant issue examined in theatre is the hardship of **parenting under difficult economic conditions**. This includes the struggles faced by female migrant workers, who are often too exhausted to fight for their maternity rights, as depicted in *World Factory*, *Shijie Gongchang* 世界工厂 (2014, dir. Zhao Chuan 赵川). *Maternity Chronicle* 生育纪事, an amateur theatre production performed by female migrant workers from Mulan Community Service Centre 北京木兰花开社工服务中心 at the Star Theatre in Beijing, shows familial inequalities. Chinese family-focused theme emerges also in *Little Emperors* 小皇帝 (2016, dir. Wang Chong 王翀; staged outside China), addressing the social and psychological impacts of China's one-child policy. The common denominator for these productions is the interest in showing the hardships of ordinary lives, and how upbringing conditions and economic challenges shape and influence relations within families. This interest can be viewed as a continuation of the long-term focus of Chinese artists on the lives of the underprivileged: rural inhabitants, migrant workers, single parents, and people in health crises.

Themes of **marriage and marital relations** are also tackled, particularly in the works of contemporary female writers and dramatists, who examine the societal expectations and disillusionment within marriages. Yang Benfen's 杨本芬 2022 unexpected hit novel *I Am Rich in Fragrance* (*Wo Ben Fenfang* 我本芬芳) sheds light on the unhappiness and confinement many women face in marriage, shaped by societal demands. Xu Kun's 徐坤 *The Sacred Marriage* (*Shensheng Hunyin* 神圣婚姻, 2023) presents a more hopeful look at marriage among affluent, globally-minded young people, suggesting that traditional institutions can offer solace amid materialism. Marital fatigue, inequality, and emotional coldness are subjects of theatrical works like *The Cat* (*Pili* 霹雳, 2021, dir. Hu Xuanyi 胡璇艺 and He Qi 何齐), which paints a picture of disintegration in marriages constrained by economic survival. The boredom, absurdity, and cruelty of marriage are explored in the performance *Talk to Her* (*Yizi* 椅子, dir. Su Xiaogang 苏小刚, Shanghai Beautiful Day Culture Studio 海美好的一天文化工作室), an adaptation of Ionesco's *The Chairs*. Films such as Feng Xiaogang's 冯小刚 *I Am Not Madame Bovary* (*Wo Bushi Pan Jinlian* 我不是潘金莲, 2016) and Qin Haiyan's 秦海燕 *The Woman in the Storm* (*Wo Jingguo Fengbao* 我经过风暴, 2023) confront the challenges of marriage, family reputation,

and domestic violence, presenting the struggles of women within constricting social systems. These works also closely touch upon the topics of gender inequality and feminism.

Relations with classmates and social peers form another interesting theme, with works often reflecting the pressure and competition embedded in early life. Bullying on campus, a lack of security embedded in the family environment, and the judgmental gaze of others are examined in Yang Zhefen's 杨哲芬 2018 play *The Flower Eaters* (*Hua Chile Na Nühai* 花吃了那女孩), Wang Chong's *Teahouse 2.0* (*Chaguan 2.0* 茶馆 2.0) staged in a real middle school classroom, and in numerous visual works by artists of the youngest generation, such as Li Han's 李涵 *Mushroom* (Mogu 蘑菇, 2023)¹. These works explore topics which can be also linked to personal traumas and feelings of detachment, discussed in the third section below.

Economic and Structural Pressures

Environmental concerns have been the focus of visual artists ever since China embarked on the rapid road of development at all costs. Pollution and waste became a central theme for works by numerous artists. Probably the best known is Wang Jiuliang 王久良, who started already in 2008 with a series of photographs and videos about waste in and around Beijing (*City Besieged by Waste*, *Laji Weicheng* 垃圾围城), switching later to projects on plastic, and on environmental destruction caused by quarrying. The famous Xu Bing 徐冰 in his *Phoenix* (*Fenghuang* 凤凰) series between 2008-2016 created monumental sculptures and installations from waste, while plastic packages became building blocks of massive installations by Wang Zhiyuan 王智远. A performance artist calling himself "Brother Nut" (Jianguo Xingdi 坚果兄弟) collected air pollution particles from Chinese city streets in 2015 using a vacuum cleaner, then moulded the toxic powder into a brick. Rural destruction has been one of the main topics for a young female artist Tong Wenmin 童文敏, who in her performances attempts to reconnect with the natural world. These and many other visual artists have consistently worked throughout the last twenty years to show the critical problem of pollution, and the **costs of rapid industrialisation and urbanisation**.

The human costs of China's economic rise are shown from an insider's perspective in a new phenomenon of "low-stratum literature" (*diceng wenxue* 底层文学). These are works written by rural migrants and other physical labourers. Fan Yusu 范雨素, a migrant nanny based in Beijing, who in 2017 penned an essay that turned her into an overnight sensation and brought this kind of literary confession into the spotlight. Her story chronicles **the struggle of millions of Chinese** in search of upward social mobility. Poetry is an important way of expression among migrant workers. *People in a Hurry: Poems by a Delivery Rider* (*Gan Shijian de Ren: Yige Waimaiyuan de Shi* 赶时间的人：一个外卖员的诗) by Wang Jibing 王计兵 was the most successful debut in poetry in 2023. Wang witnesses, experiences, and translates into poetry

¹ The works of debuting, young visual artists presented in this document were included in *Like Morn in the Day. The 17th Shanghai Youth Art Exhibition* (譬如青春。第 17 上海青年美术大展) held at the Liu Haisu Gallery in Shanghai, between 21 Oct – 29 Nov. 2023.

indignities faced by cleaners, nannies, couriers and other low-paid workers - a hot topic also in Chinese social media.

The stunning extent of urbanisation taking place in China produces a growing disparity between the city and the countryside. These socioeconomic developments bear dire consequences for individuals. Jia Pingwa 贾平凹, one of the "old masters" of Chinese literature, in 2016 published a novel *Broken Wings (Jihua 极花)* on **women trafficking** that reveals the dark realities of gender imbalance. A Yi 阿乙 writes in *Wake Me Up at 9.00 in the Morning (Zaoshang Jiudian Jiaoxing Wo 早上九点叫醒我)* about how rural inhabitants devoid of hope for social advancement become increasingly brutal and indifferent.

Cinematography is a medium especially suited to providing realistic glimpses of "other lives". *The Crossing or Walking Past the Future (Luguo Weilai 路过未来, 2017, dir. Li Ruijun 李睿珺)* are some of the films revealing **desperate attempts at upward social mobility** by those on the fringes of the society. The characters are willing to undertake risky or unconventional paths as their only way to change their economic situation. In *The Crossing*, a young girl smuggles iPhones from Hong Kong to Shenzhen, in *Walking Past the Future* another young girl endures illegal drug testing to save money for a new flat.

Chinese theatre creators have shown interest in a **critical evaluation of neoliberalism**, as a global issue, but also a part of the Chinese economic model. Chen Minghao in his 2019 adaptation of German writer Georg Kaiser's *From Morn to Midnight (Cong Qingchen Dao Wuye 从清晨到午夜)* criticises Western industrial capitalism as corrosive to the spirit, turning individuals into beings whose lives are governed solely by economic values. Similar accents pointing to spiritual emptiness, mechanical existence, and dehumanisation in a world ruled by money can be found in many other recent theatre productions, for example, *Echoing: The Seagull (Xiari shengxiang: Hai'ou 夏日声响: 海鸥)*, written by Hu Xuanyi 胡璇艺 and directed by He Qi 何齐. The economy-driven gap between traditional and modern rural life is at the heart of humorous *Hometown (Guxiang 故乡, 2021, dir. Lu Xiaoping 吕效平, Lu Xun's Hometown adaptation by Gao Ziwen 高子文)*, which shows the struggles, displacement, and spiritual depression faced by young villagers amid rural social transformation. Grass Stage's 草台班 2019 production *Wild Seeds (Caojie 草芥)* directed by Zhao Chuan 赵川 presents a critique of both capitalist and neoliberal economics, as well as existing socialist and communist ideologies. The play highlights the struggles of young urban white-collar workers shaped by China's rapid urbanization and neoliberal policies, contrasting their repetitive and solitary office work with the physical hardships endured by previous generations of labourers. *Metamorphosis (Bianxing Ji 变形记, 2021)* by Li Jianjun 李建军 criticises capitalism and labour exploitation, focusing on the extreme working conditions and human alienation faced by couriers during the Covid-19 pandemic. On the contrary, Stan Lai's 赖声川 2013 play *The Long, Narrow Passageway (Chang Gang 长巷)* points to a shift away from material wealth and toward the fulfilment found in small pleasures. Lai's work urges audiences to find contentment beyond **consumerism**, challenging societal definitions of happiness and inviting a more introspective approach to life satisfaction.

Topics of **corruption, abuse of power or state control** on various levels of business or governmental organizations are also presented in Chinese films. Genre films like Zhang Yimou's 张艺谋 crime and conspiracy thriller *Under the Light (Jian ru panshi 坚如磐石, 2023)*,

Dong Runnian's socially conscious comedy *Johnny Keep Walking!* (*Nianhui Bu Neng Ting!* 年会不能停! , 2023), Li Xiaofeng's 李霄峰 crime story *Back to the Wharf* (*Fenping Liangjing* 风平浪静, 2020) all deal with this topic, but it also appears in art-house films such as Geng Jun's 耿军 *Manchurian Tiger* (*Dongbei Hu* 东北虎, 2021) in the form of real-estate fraud or Jia Zhangke's 贾樟柯 *Mountains May Depart* (*Shanhe Guren* 山河故人, 2015), which focuses on the corruption and exploitation in mining areas. Another very important example is a film based on a true story, *Dying to Survive* (*Wo Bushi Yaoshen* 我不是药神, dir. Wen Muye 文牧野, 2018) dealing with the problem of financial inaccessibility of cancer drugs in China due to corruption in (international) business and law circles. This film not only managed to reveal an important social problem in China through a genre of tragicomedy, but according to well-informed professionals of Chinese film industry and academia² it directly contributed to a change in China's drug policies.

Films like *I Am Not Madame Bovary* and *Woman in the Storm* use personal conflicts as microcosms to expose the broader societal entanglement of the state in private life. Li Ruijun's 李睿珺 *Return to Dust* (*Yinru Chenyan* 隐入尘烟, 2022) and Liu Jie's 刘杰 *Baby* (*Baobei'er* 宝贝儿, 2018) reveal the strain of government intervention on individual and family life, whether through poverty-elimination policies or by the foster care system.

Technological advancement is an important theme in most recent works in visual arts. The last few years since the Covid-19 pandemic have accelerated artists' interest in AI, both as a tool in the artistic workshop and a topic of analysis. In numerous experimental works done with the support or in partnership with AI (e.g. presented at the *Life After Life* exhibition at the How Art Museum in Shanghai between September 2024 and February 2025), authors pose questions on human-machine interaction, the nature of humanity and the place of humans in the world of the future.

Similar topics are undertaken in the fast-growing Chinese sci-fi literature. It is now one of the most popular cultural exports of the PRC, enjoying strong state support. This literature, unsurprisingly, dissects relations between humans and technology, also in the local context. One of the most notable examples is Han Song's 韩松 powerful 2018 novel *Hospital* (*Yiyuan* 医院), showing the hopelessness of an individual posed against **omnipotent technology**.

The dystopian, high-technology-driven future is explored in theatre. *Brain Death Buffet* (*Nao Siwang Zizhucan* 脑死亡自助餐, 2023), directed by Xiao Han 姚汉, depicts a grim world where humans rent out their brains for computing tasks, becoming mere mechanized feeding systems and losing fundamental survival skills. In contrast, *Shakespeare's Garden* (*Shashibiya de Nürenmen* 莎士比亚的女人们, 2024), directed by Nie Jingzhu 聂竞竹 and written by Huang Bing 黄冰, uses Shakespeare's female characters as machine-learning data to highlight the challenges of simulating human emotions, sparking a debate about the collaboration between theatre and technology and the role of artists in navigating its risks and possibilities.

² Based on private conversations of the author during a field trip in China in October 2024.

Many of these issues are global in nature and as such they reshape lives on a level that goes far beyond the Chinese context. Works by Chinese artists and writers show that many long-recognized social issues, such as environmental pollution, poverty or corruption are still valid topics of concern in the Chinese society of today. But there are new problems as well: ageing, the use of technological tools of control, and the unknown brought about by the advent of AI.

Personal Identity and Well-Being

The last four years since the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic have put the individual in focus. The traumas of the incessant lockdowns, loneliness, and uncertainty have made their way into public narratives. Economic slowdown and the worsening of China's relations with the West have added fuel to feelings of anxiety and lack of hope. Chinese social media have been flooded with posts by youth who no longer believe in bright prospects for themselves. Terms such as "lying flat" (*tangping* 躺平), "letting it rot" (*bailan* 摆烂), references to a delusional literary character Kong Yiji (孔乙己) and "involution" (*neijuan* 内卷) have symbolised this loss of hope and the will to struggle. Another term, *run* (润) due to its phonetic proximity to the English language 'run' (as in 'run away') became a keyword for all of those young Chinese who feel that emigrating from the country is the only option.

The feeling of **disillusionment and hopelessness** resonates strongly in the works of young Chinese artists. In his 2023 painting *Tired Commuter* (*Pilao de Xingzhe* 疲劳的行者), a debuting artist Zhang Hongxuan 张鸿暄 uses the image of an exhausted teenager barely clinging to a crowded metro car, surrounded by indifferent commuters, a symbol of a young person with no place for himself in a hostile society. A similar mindset is captured in Li Jianjun's 2023 theatre adaptation of *The True Story of Ah Q* (*AQ Zhengzhuan* 阿Q正传), which examines themes of perceived inferiority, spiritual resignation, and helplessness. In Wang Chong's 2024 *Lying Flat 2.0* (*Tangping* 躺平 2.0) theatre production the "forced-to-lie-flat" actors and the audience engage in a clash between the *tangping* movement and the rise of AI dominance. One of the more strikingly recurrent topics in contemporary theatre is suicide. Meng Jinghui's 孟京辉 *The Suicide* (*Qiang, Huangyan he Meigui* 枪, 谎言和玫瑰, 2024), based on a Russian play by Edman Nikolai Robertovich, delves into the alienation and societal oppression that drive individuals to despair. Similarly, the 2024 collaborative production *Werther. Based on a novel by Johann Wolfgang von Goethe* (*Weite: Gaibian Zi Yuehan Wo'erfugang Feng Gede de Yibu Xiaoshuo* 维特: 改编自约翰·沃尔夫冈·冯·歌德的一部小说), created by the German dramaturg Sebastian Kaiser and the Nanjing University Yesoo Company 南京大学艺术硕士剧团, examines the absurd motivations behind "escaping the world". Additionally, the adaptation of Sarah Kane's *4.48* (dir. Liu Chang 刘畅) resurfaced during the 2024 Aranya Theatre Festival, revisits this haunting exploration of mental anguish.

Loneliness is the second topic clearly marked in works by young artists. Some show the feeling of isolation through hostile and towering city structures (Jiang Chucai 江楚才, Gao Chuan 高川, and Gu Peng 古鹏). Others focus on the alienation and misunderstandings within peer groups (Zhang Yanhong 张晏红, Li Han 李涵, Chen Jiaxie 陈佳玺). An intriguing work by Tian Yuhe 田雨荷 entitled *I should have had a younger sister* (*Wo yinggai you ge Meimei* 我应该有个妹妹) tells the painful story of a lonely female craving for a sibling that she knows she would

never have. Interestingly, artists have also made note of the anxieties of China's **ageing population**. In *Still Barking* (*Gou Hai Zai Jiao* 狗还在叫), a play from 2021, its author Yang Ting 杨婷 explores themes of loneliness and the unease of elderly parents, who are often closely monitored by their children, reversing the traditional family roles. This portrayal reflects the growing isolation that some older adults feel family relations evolve and shows the complex emotional currents that accompany these changes in contemporary Chinese society. A very different angle on the topic of loneliness is offered by a young sci-fi/speculative fiction author Tang Fei 糖匪 in a 2015 short story *The Path to Freedom* (*Ziyou zhi Lu* 自由之路). A family hermetically isolates itself from the outside world during a pandemic only to discover that the population adapted to it by developing extra nostrils. This simple story may be read as an expression of distancing from society or a commentary on social stagnation, written well before the real pandemic hit China and the world.

Art can also have a healing function. A process of **dealing with personal traumas** developed almost unintentionally during the first presentation of an installation and performance by a well-recognised oil painter Zhao Bandi 赵半狄. The project *Zhao Bandi's Hut* (*Zhao Bandi de Xiaowo* 赵半狄的小窝), curated by Du Xiyun 杜曦云, a successful curator specialising in social activism themes, began in November 2020 in Shanghai. The project was initially Zhao's reaction to the depressive reality of the pandemic lockdowns. Inside the gallery exhibition room, he built a cosy, safe space composed of a simple, A-shaped hut, a hammock, and plenty of straw-laden space to sit around. Ordinary visitors were invited to join the artist in his haven, drink, eat and talk freely. The installation soon developed into group self-help sessions, during which the visitors talked about their traumas, well-hidden family tragedies or loneliness³. The hut travelled to multiple cities, and wherever it went, it sparked a similarly warm welcome. Many of the visitors' stories were recorded, and now make a constantly expanding archive available on the curator Du's personal WeChat Channel. The project uncovers a strong need in Chinese society to work through personal traumas which are sometimes well hidden from family members and friends, but manifest themselves in a safe, welcoming space, among strangers.

Trauma transformed into feminist art is strongly present in theatre. Using dreamlike and profoundly poetic aesthetics, the director and playwright Zhou Zhongyu 周仲玉 shares her personal experience as a victim of sexual violence and systemic oppression in the 2013 play *El Fondo un Campo de Nieve* (*Ru Jintian Wo Yansude Zai Xueyuanshang Fengbu Ai yu Meng Jing* 如今我严肃地在雪原上缝补爱与梦境). Inspired by Eve Ensler's renowned *The Vagina Monologues*, the 2018 play *The Penis Monologues* (*Yinjing Dubai* 阴茎独白), directed by sexologist Fang Gang 方刚, delves into themes such as male vulnerability, societal definitions of masculinity, and the often-taboo discussions surrounding male sexuality. The feminist approach is also introduced through drawing on historic examples of remarkable women. The 2021 play *When We Two Parted* (*Chunshi* 春逝), directed by Zhu Hongxuan 朱虹璇, focuses on two significant female physicists: Gu Jinghui 顾静徽 and Wu Jianxiong 吴健雄. There is an

³ A thorough description of the project can be found in *Art Absolute* (*Juedui yishu*) No. 12/2021.03, pp. 13-41.

ongoing discussion about the challenges female performers face in their everyday work, particularly regarding the use of their bodies. A strong feminist statement on the artist's body, which remains the subject of constant evaluation, is at the core of Tan Tan's 炭叹 2017 performance *Female Artist Must Be Beautiful; Female Artist Must Use Her Body* (Nü Yishujia shi Meide; Nü Yishujia Bixu Shiyong Zijide Shenti 女艺术家是美的; 女艺术家必须使用自己的身体), which is dedicated to a female artist Baroness Elsa von Freytag-Loringhoven who has long been erased from history but is now considered a likely author of many groundbreaking and highly valued works traditionally attributed to male artists (e.g., Marcel Duchamp's *Fountain*). There are also strong feminist threads in visual arts, with artist-performers such as Cao Yu 曹雨 and her powerful works: *Faucet* (Longtou 龙头), *Fountain* (Quan 泉) or the *I Have* (Wo You 我有) series.

In the post-pandemic world, it is no way unique for Chinese artists to be focussing on personal traumas and to be tackling loneliness and alienation in their works. What makes the Chinese experience different, however, is the concurrence of these themes with that of the loss of hope and motivation caused by economic and political shifts.

Ways of voicing social critique

Many topics of social interest are politically charged and taking them on by artists and writers involves certain risks. The Chinese censorship system is effective in its unique flexibility and localisation. The rules are general and vague. It is up to the organiser of a performance (e.g. theatre festival), publisher (literary work), film producer or gallery owner to interpret them correctly and know what can and cannot be said and shown. In the event of wrong judgment and failure to receive the necessary approval for the event or dissemination of a literary work or film, all responsibility rests firmly on the shoulders of these people and the artists. Final decisions are localised through the Central Propaganda Department and other institutions' local branches, whose interpretation can vary and take into consideration local conditions. Initial approval can be withdrawn at any time, also for books that have already been published, and films that have already started to be screened. Self-censorship by the creators themselves, and "preventive" censorship by producers, event organisers, and publishers becomes the most widespread and the most effective tool of control. No gallery or publishing house wishes to be closed, no theatre festival wishes to be cancelled, and no film producer wants to see a film in which millions of RMB were invested being prevented from distribution and cut away from profit-making.

Artists who decide to continue commenting on the social reality of today's China try to find ways and strategies to do so within the boundaries of what is permitted. Similarly to Eastern Europe in the socialist era, Chinese artists proactively and creatively explore various means of indirect communication with their audiences, using allusions and other subtle means. Forest Young (Yang Yexin 杨烨妍), a Shanghai-based advertisement creator by day and a visual and performance artist by night, has created a series of works entitled *No talking today* (*Jintian Bu Shuo Hua* 今天不说话), with a common element of himself or other people photographed or filmed wearing face masks with the slogan "No talking today" in Chinese written on them, positioned against various backgrounds. The powerful message of critique through silence

has been used by this artist since 2014 to explore topics such as urban space demolition and evictions, pollution or poverty⁴.

Another strong message of silent protest was offered by the famous painter Huang Rui⁵ 黄锐 in February 2022, right after the Russian military invasion of Ukraine. Huang Rui was probably the only artist in Mainland China who decided to openly react against the official propaganda and voice his criticism of the Russian imperialist aggression. His painting series *The Lack of Peace* (*Heping zhi Que* 和平之缺) consisting of abstract paintings exploring Ukrainian national colours of blue and yellow, with round holes cut through the canvas was presented at the *Together for Peace* exhibition organised at the premises of the Polish Embassy in Beijing (as a space outside the reach of Chinese censors) in March 2022. The message of the anti-war protest was all too clear.

Some artists are more explicit in their critiques. In 2017, the visual artist and performer Zhao Zhao 赵赵, a native of Xinjiang, arranged for a real camel and its keeper to travel from his home region to a gallery in Beijing's 798 Art Zone (*Desert Camel, Shamo: Luotuo* 沙漠·骆驼). It proved that it was much easier for the animal to travel across China than for its keeper who was stopped numerous times and was subject to restrictive policies of the Chinese state directed at the Xinjiang population. The same artist in 2019 created a project named *Control* (*Kongzhi* 控制), in which he shows how the shape of a gourd can be crafted during its growth. Human control can shape a gourd as is wished. The analogy to the state's control over its citizens feels very easy to read.

In literature, two interesting approaches can be noticed, representing strategies preferred by older and younger generation writers. Senior writers, such as Yan Lianke or Mo Yan in their social critique often resort to fable or farce. Sometimes, they create intricate and elaborate allegories through which they voice their critique or shift the action to imperial China. Younger writers opt for a more toned-down aesthetic that reflects a "knowing but not speaking" attitude. A calm distrust toward the official (historical) narratives is seen in Zhang Yueran's 张悦然 work *Cocoon* (*Chong* 茧, 2016), Qian Jianan's 钱佳楠 *A Girl Who Wouldn't Eat Eggs* (*Buchi Jidan de Ren* 不吃鸡蛋的人, 2018), or Shuang Xuetao's 双雪涛 *Moses on a Plain* (*Pingyuan Shang de Moxi* 平原上的摩西, 2020). The former two seem very aware of the fragility of an individual in China, yet their protagonists do not endorse the older generations' pragmatism. Especially worthy of notice in this context is a dynamic group of young authors from China's Northeast areas known as Dongbei (the North-East), sometimes referred to as "China's Belt of Rust" - an area that in the 1990s experienced massive lay-offs, deindustrialization, and economic decline. Now, its culture (and pop culture) is generating new interest across the country, labelled the "Dongbei Renaissance". Young Dongbei writers include Ban Yu (班宇), Shuang Xuetao, and Zheng Zhi (郑执). They represent the "son

⁴ Forest Young ran his own art gallery in M50 in Shanghai until 2024 where he exhibited his artworks from the "No talking today" series.

⁵ Huang Rui was one of the founding members of the famous Stars Art Group, organising the first contemporary art exhibitions in China after the initiation of the Reform and Opening Up policy changes in 1979. While all other key members of the group have emigrated from China in the 1980s and continue living abroad, Huang returned from his exile in Japan in 2001 and lives and works in Beijing. He was instrumental in creating the 798 Art Zone.

generation" – descendants of laid-off workers. Their focus on a largely forgotten period of traumatic transformation can be interpreted, somewhat surprisingly, as a longing for stability and relief from anxiety. Xinhua Agency, in a recently deleted article, called their works "sincere", but also added that "we don't want to see wallowing" (NYT, 2024).

In film, we can identify several basic approaches to how the artists express social critique and avoid censorship at the same time:

a) Explanatory and didactic postscripts

In many movies of different topics and genres, we can find "postscripts" at the very end of the movie explaining how the story relates to Chinese realities and policies. They can be interpreted as safety nets for the creators who in this way justify the critical notes of their works. *Old Town Girls* (*Tuzi baoli* 兔子暴力, 2021, dir. Shen Yu 申瑜), a film (among other things) about kidnapping, ends with a postscript stating that all characters were punished according to the law. *Woman in the Storm* closes with a statement about newly appointed government policies related to domestic violence. Zhang Yimou's film *Under the Light* ends with a message about the PRC's government anti-corruption policies.

b) Marginal spaces

Many of the films tackling social topics (critiques directed at state officials or productions merely showing poverty, lack of social harmony, or crime) are set in spaces somewhat on the margins of Chinese society. In this way, the critique can be seen as non-representative of China as a whole. Examples of such approaches include but are not limited to, Yang Heng's 杨恒 2017 film *Ghost in the Mountains* (*Kongshan Yike* 空山异客), Cai Changjie's 蔡成杰 2017 production *Mirrors and Feathers* (*Beifang Yipian Cangmang* 北方一片苍茫), Zhou Ziyang's 周子阳 2020 film *Wu Hai* 乌海, or Geng Jun's *Manchurian Tiger*.

c) Film genres

In the past years film directors tried escaping the rigid guidelines of the censorship system by embracing specific film genres, such as thriller or film noir, and slipping social critique into the otherwise genre-typical plots. Examples of such films include Li Xiaofeng's *Back to the Wharf* or Zhang Yimou's *Under the Light*, which Zhang still had a lot of trouble releasing⁶. A more recent trend is using the genre of comedy as a vehicle for subtle social critique. Films such as Ning Yuanyuan's 宁元元 *An Insignificant Affair* (*Xiao Shi'er* 小事儿), Wen Muye's 文牧野 2022 film *Nice View* (*Qiji: Ben Xiaohai* 奇迹·笨小孩), Xu Zheng's 徐峥 more serious 2024 production

⁶ It took the film 4 years to get through the censorship process and the original script had to undergo significant changes. Nowadays, it is very hard to find descriptions of these troubles in mainstream media, with articles on the topic often disappearing. However, there are some widely read blogs available describing the reasons for the script adjustments as well as specific corrections made in it. See for example the post "Who Does Zhang Yimou's *Under the Light* Actually Shine Upon? Why Did It Suffer a Chain of Revisions?"

(张艺谋电影《坚如磐石》究竟在映射谁? 为何惨遭连环删改?)

https://web.archive.org/web/20241202185542/https://www.sohu.com/a/725739258_256797

Upstream (Nixing Rensheng 逆行人生) or Dong Runnian's *Johnny Keep Walking!* aim for commercial success, but touch upon important social issues.

Chinese theatre embraces metaphor and allegory, and due to its inherent flexibility, production contents are often adjusted to a specific stage, time, and context. While scripts need to go through censorship, theatre directors and their casts retain some freedom as to how a given play is produced on a given stage and on a given day. There are locations where more is permitted and where every word pronounced on stage is monitored closely by vigilant officials sitting in the audience. Renowned playwright and theatre director Meng Jinghui 孟京辉 knows the system as best as anyone in China. His recent production *The Bedbug* (*Chouchong* 臭虫) can serve as a good example illustrating both the use of metaphorical stage language, and spatial flexibility. Meng himself admits to changing his interpretation of the script with each staging. When presented in 2023 at the Wuzhen International Theatre Festival, *The Bedbug* was already running through its fourth rendition. On the Wuzhen stage, it became a poignant critique of an evolving China, grappling with an identity crisis amid shifting ideologies. Some of the sentences spoken on that festival stage would not have been permitted in any theatre in Beijing. The festival, far away from the capital, as an “artistic bubble” sealed away from wider audiences, was a place and time when much more was permissible, and Meng used this opportunity to the utmost.

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